

Structure-Based Molecular Docking and ADME Profiling of Novel Thienopyrimidines as Dual VEGFR/EGFR Inhibitors in Colorectal Cancer

Priya A *, Shachindra L. Nargund, Mahesh Kumar N and Sharmila A. Gote

Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, Nargund College of Pharmacy, Bengaluru-560085, India.

World Journal of Biology Pharmacy and Health Sciences, 2025, 23(01), 528-536

Publication history: Received on 14 June 2025; revised on 26 July 2025; accepted on 29 July 2025

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjbphs.2025.23.1.0716>

Abstract

Colorectal cancer (CRC) is one of the leading causes of cancer-related deaths globally, contributing to nearly 10% of all cancer cases and 9.4% of cancer mortalities, as reported by recent GLOBOCAN data. Targeting receptor tyrosine kinases such as vascular endothelial growth factor receptor (VEGFR) and epidermal growth factor receptor (EGFR) has become a vital strategy in cancer therapeutics due to their key roles in tumor angiogenesis and cell proliferation. In this study, a series of novel thienopyrimidine derivatives were computationally evaluated for their potential as dual inhibitors of VEGFR and EGFR using a structure-based drug design approach. The crystal structures of VEGFR2 (PDB ID: 6GQP) and EGFR (PDB ID: 5D41) were retrieved from the Protein Data Bank and prepared using AutoDock Tools. Thienopyrimidine derivatives were designed using ChemDraw, energy-minimized, and converted into 3D structures. Molecular docking simulations were conducted using AutoDock Vina within PyRx, and protein-ligand interactions were analyzed using PyMOL and Discovery Studio. Docking results revealed that compounds PAS1 and PAS9 exhibited the highest binding affinities toward both EGFR (-8.7 kcal/mol) and VEGFR (-8.6 and -8.0 kcal/mol, respectively), outperforming the reference drug Lenvatinib (-8.3 and -7.9 kcal/mol). Pharmacokinetic properties assessed using SwissADME indicated that most compounds complied with Lipinski's rule of five, and demonstrated favorable absorption, bioavailability, and blood-brain barrier permeability. Overall, this study suggests that thienopyrimidine scaffolds possess promising dual-inhibitory potential and favorable drug-like properties, supporting their development as targeted therapies for colorectal cancer.

Keywords: Colorectal cancer; Dual inhibition; EGFR; Molecular docking; Thienopyrimidines; VEGFR

1. Introduction

Colorectal cancer (CRC) is one of the leading causes of cancer-related morbidity and mortality globally. Despite the development of targeted therapies, treatment resistance and compensatory signaling pathways remain major obstacles in achieving long-term disease control [1]. Among the most well-characterized drivers of CRC progression are vascular endothelial growth factor receptor 2 (VEGFR-2) and epidermal growth factor receptor (EGFR), which mediate tumor angiogenesis and proliferative signaling, respectively [2]. Recent therapeutic strategies have shifted toward the simultaneous inhibition of multiple targets to enhance efficacy and overcome resistance mechanisms. Dual inhibition of VEGFR-2 and EGFR is increasingly recognized as a promising approach to block redundant oncogenic pathways and suppress both tumor vascularization and cell growth [3]. For example, 4,6-diaryl pyrimidines have demonstrated potent dual inhibitory activity against VEGFR-2 and EGFR in CRC models [4]. Likewise, S-alkylated quinazolinone analogues have shown encouraging antiproliferative activity and strong binding affinity toward both targets in computational docking studies [5]. Heterocyclic frameworks such as thienopyrimidines have garnered significant attention due to their structural similarity to purine bases, allowing for strong interactions within the ATP-binding clefts of kinases [6]. Several thienopyrimidine derivatives have been designed and evaluated as selective EGFR inhibitors with anticancer properties [7]. Others have been synthesized as dual inhibitors of VEGFR-2 and EGFR, exhibiting robust docking scores and

* Corresponding author: Priya A

favorable biological activities [8]. The design and optimization of dual-target inhibitors are increasingly guided by computational approaches, which offer cost-effective and efficient alternatives to traditional screening. In silico techniques such as molecular docking, ADME (absorption, distribution, metabolism, and excretion) profiling, and molecular dynamics simulations are now integral to early-stage drug discovery [9]. These tools provide critical insights into receptor–ligand interactions, predict pharmacokinetic behavior, and facilitate the rational design of lead compounds [10]. Recent studies employing such computational strategies have reported novel dihydropyrimidine and quinazoline derivatives with promising VEGFR-2/EGFR dual-inhibitory profiles [11]. Similarly, novel thienopyrimidine analogues incorporating arylidene or triazole moieties have shown strong binding affinity and selectivity toward both targets [12]. Pyrazole and benzimidazole hybrids have also demonstrated dual-target activity, supported by docking, ADME, and in vitro anticancer evaluations [13]. Advanced machine learning-assisted docking has further accelerated the discovery of multi-kinase inhibitors, including those with dual EGFR and VEGFR-2 activity [14]. Substituted thiophenyl-pyrimidines and thieno[2,3-d] pyrimidines have recently been developed with excellent dual-target potential and are currently under investigation for colorectal cancer treatment [15].

Figure 1 Association and inhibition of EGFR and VEGF pathways [16]

Given this background, our current research study focuses on the structure-based design, molecular docking, and ADME profiling of novel thienopyrimidine derivatives for dual inhibition of VEGFR-2 and EGFR in CRC. As part of this study, Lenvatinib, a known multitargeted tyrosine kinase inhibitor with established activity against VEGFRs and EGFR, is employed as a reference standard to benchmark the performance of the newly designed compounds. Through computational methods, we aim to evaluate binding affinities, predict pharmacokinetic parameters, and prioritize molecules with favourable drug-likeness and target engagement. This integrated computational strategy serves to identify potent candidates for future synthetic and biological validation.

2. Materials and methods

A total of nine thieno[2,3-d] pyrimidine derivatives were selected for computational evaluation. The 2D chemical structures were sketched using ChemDraw and structurally optimized for accurate geometry before docking. Molecular docking was performed using AutoDock Vina integrated with PyRx, targeting two key proteins implicated in colorectal cancer: epidermal growth factor receptor (EGFR, PDB ID: 5D41) and vascular endothelial growth factor receptor 2 (VEGFR-2, PDB ID: 6GQP). Docking simulations yielded binding affinity values (in kcal/mol), enabling the ranking of compounds based on their receptor interactions. The most promising candidates were subsequently evaluated for their absorption, distribution, metabolism, and excretion (ADME) properties using the SwissADME platform. Parameters

assessed included Lipinski's Rule of Five, gastrointestinal absorption, aqueous solubility, and bioavailability, aiding in the identification of drug-like molecules for further development.

2.1. Protein Selection and Preparation

The X-ray crystallographic structures of VEGFR-2 (PDB ID: 6GQP) and EGFR (PDB ID: 5D41) were retrieved from the Protein Data Bank (PDB). The proteins were prepared using AutoDock Tools, where all water molecules, ligands, and heteroatoms were removed. Polar hydrogens were added, and Kollman charges were assigned. The prepared structures were then saved in PDBQT format for docking.

2.2. Ligand Preparation

A set of nine novel thienopyrimidine derivatives (PAS1–PAS9) were designed and drawn using ChemDraw, and 3D structures were energy minimized using Open Babel in PyRx. Lenvatinib, a clinically approved dual inhibitor of VEGFR and EGFR, was included as the reference compound. All ligands were converted to PDBQT format after energy minimization for docking simulations.

Figure 2 Structures of thieno[2,3-d] pyrimidine derivatives PAS1-PAS9

2.3. Active Site Prediction

The active sites of EGFR (PDB ID: 5D41) and VEGFR2 (PDB ID: 6GQP) were identified using literature data and validated through a computational tool, i.e. CASTp server. For EGFR, key residues in the ATP-binding pocket include Met793, Leu718, Lys745, and Asp855, which are essential for ligand interaction and stabilization. VEGFR2's active site is defined by residues such as Cys919, Lys868, Glu885, and Asp1046, forming a well-conserved catalytic cleft suitable for inhibitor

binding. These regions were targeted during molecular docking to ensure optimal alignment of ligands within biologically relevant pockets, aiding the evaluation of thienopyrimidines as dual VEGFR/EGFR inhibitors.

2.4. Molecular Docking Protocol

Molecular docking was performed using AutoDock Vina integrated within PyRx software. The grid box was adjusted to cover the ATP-binding sites of both EGFR and VEGFR-2, based on the co-crystallized ligand positions. Exhaustiveness was set to 8, and docking was performed under default parameters. Binding affinity values (kcal/mol) were recorded and ranked.

2.5. ADME Prediction

The drug-likeness and pharmacokinetic profiles of the designed molecules were assessed using SwissADME (www.swissadme.ch). Parameters including molecular weight (MW), hydrogen bond donors (HBD), hydrogen bond acceptors (HBA), lipophilicity (LogP), topological polar surface area (TPSA), number of rotatable bonds, and Lipinski's rule of five compliance were evaluated. Molecules with favorable ADME properties were prioritized for further consideration.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Molecular Docking Analysis

To assess the potential of novel thienopyrimidine-based derivatives as dual VEGFR2 and EGFR inhibitors, molecular docking simulations were performed using AutoDock Vina integrated within PyRx. The selected target proteins included VEGFR2 (PDB ID: 6GQP) and EGFR (PDB ID: 5D41). Lenvatinib, a clinically approved multi-kinase inhibitor, was employed as the reference compound. Several thienopyrimidine derivatives demonstrated superior binding affinities compared to lenvatinib. Notably, PAS1, PAS3, and PAS9 exhibited docking scores of -8.7 kcal/mol against EGFR, which is more favorable than lenvatinib's score of -8.3 kcal/mol. Similarly, PAS1 and PAS2 showed better or comparable interaction energies with VEGFR2 than the reference compound. These results suggest that thienopyrimidine scaffolds possess promising dual-target inhibitory potential.

Table 1 Docking Scores of Novel Thieno[2,3-d] pyrimidine Derivatives.

Compound Code	Vina Score EGFR (kcal/mol)	Vina Score VEGFR (kcal/mol)
PAS1	-8.7	-8.6
PAS2	-8.1	-8.4
PAS3	-8.7	-7.9
PAS4	-7.9	-8.4
PAS5	-7.4	-8.2
PAS6	-7.2	-6.7
PAS7	-8.1	-7.7
PAS8	-8.4	-8.1
PAS9	-8.7	-8.0
Lenvatinib	-8.3	-7.9

3.2. Comparative Analysis and Implications

Among the tested compounds, PAS1, PAS3, and PAS9 demonstrated notable binding affinities across both targets, suggesting effective dual inhibition potential. The presence of conserved interactions with key hinge and catalytic residues in both EGFR and VEGFR2 supports the structural compatibility of thienopyrimidine scaffolds for multitarget engagement. These findings underscore the promise of these derivatives as lead candidates for further optimization and in vitro validation in the context of colorectal cancer therapy.

Figure 7 3D and 2D interaction of PAS9 with VEGFR (6GQP)

3.3. ADME Profiling

To evaluate the drug-likeness and pharmacokinetic behaviour of the designed thienopyrimidine derivatives, ADME (Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism, and Excretion) analysis was performed using the SwissADME web tool. The assessment was divided into two key components: physicochemical properties and pharmacokinetic predictions, which play a crucial role in determining oral bioavailability, solubility, membrane permeability, and systemic circulation behaviour of the compounds.

3.3.1. Physicochemical Properties

According to Lipinski's Rule of Five, ideal oral drugs should have a molecular weight under 500 g/mol, $\text{LogP} \leq 5$, no more than 5 HBDs, and no more than 10 HBAs.

Table 2 Physicochemical Properties of Thienopyrimidine Derivatives and Lenvatinib.

Compound Code	MW (g/mol)	LogP (Consensus)	HBD	HBA	TPSA (\AA^2)	Rotatable Bonds	Lipinski Violations
PAS1	306.36	1.57	2	5	134.59	3	0
PAS2	272.28	2.22	1	4	111.87	3	0
PAS3	317.28	1.60	1	6	157.69	4	0
PAS4	268.24	2.50	1	5	63.11	0	0
PAS5	296.39	2.72	0	2	60.50	2	0
PAS6	417.06	2.24	1	4	108.93	1	0
PAS7	341.39	2.21	0	4	106.32	3	0
PAS8	364.39	3.84	0	5	60.50	3	0
PAS9	314.38	3.13	0	3	60.50	2	0
Lenvatinib	426.85	3.52	1	6	94.99	7	0

All compounds complied with Lipinski's Rule of Five, with none exceeding the acceptable limits of MW (<500 g/mol), LogP (<5), HBD (≤ 5), HBA (≤ 10), and rotatable bonds (≤ 10). The molecular weights of the compounds ranged from 268.24 to 417.06 g/mol, well below the upper limit, ensuring favourable oral drug-likeness. PAS6 and Lenvatinib were the heaviest molecules, but still within an acceptable range. LogP values ranged from 1.57 to 3.84, indicating balanced lipophilicity for membrane permeability. PAS8 showed the highest LogP (3.84), indicating higher lipophilicity, potentially favoring membrane permeability, but may raise concerns with aqueous solubility. TPSA values remained within acceptable limits (<140 \AA^2) for all compounds except PAS3 (157.69 \AA^2), which may affect intestinal absorption.

Lower TPSA values (as seen in PAS4, PAS5, PAS8, and PAS9) are generally associated with improved cell membrane permeability. None of the compounds violated any of Lipinski's rules, indicating good oral bioavailability potential and strong drug-like characteristics.

3.3.2. Pharmacokinetic (ADME) Properties

Pharmacokinetic descriptors such as Gastrointestinal (GI) absorption, Bioavailability Score, Blood–Brain Barrier (BBB) permeation, and P-glycoprotein (P-gp) substrate/inhibitor status were also assessed. These characteristics provide a deeper understanding of how each compound may behave in vivo.

Table 3 ADME Properties of PAS1–PAS9 and Lenvatinib.

Compound Code	GI Absorption	BBB Permeant	P-gp Substrate	Bioavailability Score	Drug-likeness
PAS1	High	No	No	0.55	Yes
PAS2	High	No	No	0.55	Yes
PAS3	Low*	No	Yes	0.55	Yes
PAS4	High	Yes	No	0.55	Yes
PAS5	High	Yes	No	0.55	Yes
PAS6	High	No	Yes	0.55	Yes
PAS7	High	No	No	0.55	Yes
PAS8	High	Yes	No	0.55	Yes
PAS9	High	Yes	No	0.55	Yes
Lenvatinib	High	No	Yes	0.55	Yes

Most of the thienopyrimidine derivatives showed high predicted GI absorption, indicating good potential for oral uptake. Compounds PAS4, PAS5, PAS8, and PAS9 were predicted to be BBB permeant, suggesting possible central nervous system activity, which may be advantageous or require caution depending on the target disease. PAS3, PAS6, and Lenvatinib were identified as P-gp substrates, potentially reducing intracellular accumulation due to active efflux.

4. Conclusion

This computational study explored the potential of novel thiophene-linked pyrimidine derivatives (PAS1–PAS9) as dual inhibitors targeting VEGFR2 (PDB ID: 6GQP) and EGFR (PDB ID: 5D41), which are both implicated in the progression and angiogenesis of colorectal cancer. Compounds PAS1, PAS3, and PAS9 showed superior binding affinity compared to Lenvatinib, as confirmed by molecular docking. ADME profiling indicated no Lipinski violations, good GI absorption, and acceptable physicochemical properties. PAS4, PAS5, PAS8, and PAS9 were predicted to cross the blood–brain barrier (BBB), while PAS1 and PAS3 exhibited favorable pharmacokinetics without P-gp substrate behavior. These findings support PAS1, PAS3, and PAS9 as promising leads for further development as dual VEGFR/EGFR-targeting agents in colorectal cancer.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

The authors extend their sincere thanks to the Management of Nargund College of Pharmacy and the Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry for their infrastructural facilitation that contributed significantly to the successful completion of this research work.

Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

- [1] Mostafa YA, Assoud JA, Desoky AY, Mohamady S, Mohamed NM, Salem OIA, et al. New series of 4,6-diaryl pyrimidines: facile synthesis and antiproliferative activity as dual EGFR/VEGFR-2 inhibitors. *Front Chem.* 2024; 12:1498104.
- [2] Tawfik SS, Hamdi A, Ali AR, Elgazar AA, El-Shafey HW, El-Azab AS, et al. S-Alkylated quinazolin-4(3H)-ones as dual EGFR/VEGFR-2 kinase inhibitors: design, synthesis, anticancer evaluation and docking study. *RSC Adv.* 2024; 14:26325–26339.
- [3] Al-Wahaibi LH, Elshamsy AM, Ali TFS, Youssif BGM. Design and synthesis of new dihydropyrimidine derivatives with a cytotoxic effect as dual EGFR/VEGFR-2 inhibitors. *ACS Omega.* 2024; 9(32):34358–34369.
- [4] Geesi MH. New quinazoline-N-4-fluorophenyl derivatives as potential anticancer agents: discovery of a promising dual EGFR/VEGFR-2 inhibitor. *J King Saud Univ Sci.* 2024; 36:103518.
- [5] Elsebaie HA, El-Bastawissy EA, Elberembally KM, Khaleel EF, Badi RM, Shaldam MA, et al. Novel 4-(2-arylidenehydrazineyl) thienopyrimidine derivatives as anticancer EGFR inhibitors: design, synthesis, biological evaluation, kinome selectivity and in silico insights. *Bioorg Chem.* 2023; 140:106799.
- [6] Sultan S. Design, synthesis and molecular docking of new thieno[2,3-d] pyrimidin-4-one derivatives as dual EGFR and FGFR inhibitors. *Drug Dev Res.* 2025; 86(1): e70061.
- [7] El-Hazek et al. Development of new thieno[2,3-d] pyrimidines as dual EGFR and STAT3 inhibitors with anticancer activity. *Bioorg Chem.* 2024; 142:106999.
- [8] Anwer KE, El-Hddad SSA, Abd El-Sattar NEA, et al. Five and six-membered heterocyclic rings with azobenzene as dual EGFR^{T790M} and VEGFR-2 inhibitors: in silico ADMET profile, docking, simulation, and anticancer evaluation. *RSC Adv.* 2023; 13:35321–35338.
- [9] Abdel Aziz et al. Recent updates on thienopyrimidine derivatives as anticancer agents. *Med Chem Res.* 2023;32(6):803–820.
- [10] El-Metwally SA, Elkady HA, Hagrass M, Husein DZ, Ibrahim IM, Taghour MS, et al. Design and synthesis of new thieno[2,3-d] pyrimidines targeting VEGFR-2: docking and MD simulation studies. *RSC Adv.* 2023;13(33):23365–23385.
- [11] Ihmaid et al. Benzimidazole–1,2,3-triazole hybrids as EGFR inhibitors: synthesis, docking, and in vitro studies. *Front Chem.* 2024; 12:1541846.
- [12] El-Hazek et al. Thiazoloquinolinone derivatives as VEGFR-2 inhibitors: docking, MD simulation, and pharmacological evaluation. *BMC Chem.* 2025; 19:90.
- [13] Abdelgawad MA, Musa A, Almalki AH, et al. Pyrazole and pyrazolopyridine derivatives as dual EGFR/VEGFR-2 inhibitors: design, docking and biological evaluation. *Drug Dev Res.* 2025;86(1): e70056.
- [14] Rezaee P, Rezaee S, Maaza M, Arab SS. Machine learning and docking-based screening of dual-target ligands for EGFR and VEGFR. *arXiv preprint.* 2024;2405.00647.
- [15] Al-Muntaser SM, El-Naggar AM, Ali AK, Abbass EM. Novel 4-thiophenyl-pyrimidine derivatives as dual inhibitors of EGFR and VEGFR-2: synthesis, docking, and in vitro studies. *RSC Adv.* 2023; 13:12184–12203.
- [16] Wang Q, Zeng A, Zhu M, Song L. Dual inhibition of EGFR-VEGF: An effective approach to the treatment of advanced non-small cell lung cancer with EGFR mutation. *Int J Oncol.* 2023; 62:26.